

The Influence of Work Discipline and Employee Skills on Work Productivity with Work Motivation as A Moderation Variable in Pandemi Time of Covid 19

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Keywords

Abstract

Work discipline;

Employee skills;

Work motivation;

Work productivity;

Covid-19;

Generally, the purpose of the research are 1) to know and analyze the effect of work discipline on work productivity, 2) to know and analyze the effect of employee skills on work productivity, 3) to know and analyze the effect of work motivation on work productivity, 4) to know and analyze whether motivation work moderates the effect of work discipline on work productivity, 5) Knowing and analyzing whether work motivation moderates the effect of employee skills on work productivity during the Covid 19 Pandemic in goods delivery service companies at the KCU Jakarta Premier Post Office 13000. The unit of analysis is all employees of the post office post office KCU Jakarta Premier 13000 with a total of 257 employees. The observation unit was 72 employees of the KCU Jakarta Premier 13000 post office. The research method is a quantitative. It is concluded that work discipline has a positive and significant effect on work productivity during the Covid 19 pandemic; Work skills did not have a significant effect on work productivity, while work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work productivity, but work motivation did not mediate the influence of work discipline on work productivity.

1. Introduction

Productivity is a comparison between the results achieved (output) with all resources (input) used per unit time. It contains ways or methods, although in theory it can be done but in practice it is

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difficult to implement because the input resources used generally consist of many kinds with different proportions (Hasibuan, 2017).

Work productivity is a measurement and quantity of work by considering all costs and related matters and those required for the job. From this explanation, it can be concluded that work productivity is a measure that compares the quality and quantity of employees in units of time to use the resources used in order to obtain results and work performance effectively and efficiently (Butar,2015). Productivity is the comparison between the results achieved with the participation of labor per unit of time. The participation of the workforce here is the effective and efficient use of resources (Kusrianto & Sutrisno 2017). The ability to produce goods and services from various resources or production factors that are used to improve the quality and quantity of work produced in a company. In every company, work productivity is very important, because in running a business this is a benchmark for the success of the business (Sendow,2019).

Motivation is a condition or energy that drives employees who are directed or directed to achieve the company's organizational goals. Motivation is formed from the attitude of employees in dealing with work situations in the company (Mangkunegara,2016). Motivation is a desire within a person that causes that person to act. People usually act for a reason to achieve a goal. So motivation is a drive that is governed by a purpose and rarely appears in a vacuum. The words need, want, desire, and drive are all similar to motive from which the word motivation is derived (Mathis & Jackson, 2017).

work discipline, it is also a company action to direct the company's members to comply with various existing company regulations (Iptian,2020). Work discipline is needed to support all organizational activities' smooth running so that organizational goals can be maximally achieved. Work discipline can be seen as an excellent benefit for the organization's use and employees' interests. For organizations, work discipline will ensure that order is maintained and the execution of tasks is smooth to obtain optimal results. As for employees, a pleasant working atmosphere will be accepted to increase morale in carrying out their work (Duchon & Plowman,2005). skills are the ability of a person to carry out an activity or job as a skill or expertise to do a job that is only required by practice (Lian ,2013). defines skills not only related to a person's expertise to do something tangible. Apart from physical, the meaning of skill also refers to a person's mental, manual, motor, perceptual and even social abilities issues (Irianto,2016).

2. Research Methods

Determination of the population is an important stage in research (Sugiyono,2018). The population in this study were all employees of the KCU Jakarta Premier 13000 post office. The composition of employees at the KCU Jakarta Premier 13000 post office. According to Sugiyono, sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population. The sample was taken because researchers have limitations in conducting research both in terms of time, energy, funds and a very large population. So, researchers must take samples that are truly representative.

3. Results and Discussion

Validity Test Results

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(Ali Moalim Ahmed Maow, Dedi Purwana, Indra Pahala)*

Based on the PLS method, testing the validity of reflexive indicators is carried out in 2 stages. The first stage is testing convergent validity, namely testing validity based on the loading factor value of each construct, and the second stage is testing discriminant validity, namely testing validity based on comparisons.

Convergent Validity

Testing the validity of the first stage is used to identify that the unobserved variable can be measured using each observed variable construct through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) or commonly referred to as factor analysis by looking at the loading factor. Loading factor is a number that shows the correlation between the score of an item in question and the score of the construct indicators that measure the construct. The loading factor value greater than 0.70 is said to be valid. After processing the data using SmartPLS 3.0, the loading factor results are presented in Figure 1. as follows:

Source: Results of analysis using SmartPLS 3.0. (2023)

Based on figure 1. above, it is known that the loading factor values are summarized in following Table 1:

No.	Indicator	Work Discipline (X ₁)	Employee Skills (X ₂)	Work motivation (Z)	Work productivity (Y)
1.	Item_01	0.752	0.727	0.796	0.814
2.	Item_02	0.720	0.767	0.802	0.761
3.	Item_03	0.812	0.751	0.739	0.836
4.	Item_04	0.832	0.747	0.766	0.324
5.	Item_05	0.795	0.714	0.820	0.785
6.	Item_06	0.842	0.825	0.766	0.769
7.	Item_07	0.760	0.818	0.852	0.869
8.	Item_08	0.758	0.758	0.830	0.729
9.	Item_09	0.786	0.755	0.818	0.792
10.	Item_10	0.744	0.753	0.747	0.833

11.	Item_11	0.775	0.810	0.728	0.796
12.	Item_12	0.232	0.545	0.787	0.743
13.	Item_13	0.413	0.821	0.436	0.857
14.	Item_14	0.833	0.827	0.821	0.863
15.	Item_15	0.705	0.771	0.814	0.470
16.	Item_16		0.824	0.833	
17.	Item_17		0.504		
18.	Item_18		0.756		

Source: Results of analysis using SmartPLS 3.0. (2023)

The results of the validity test are in Table 1. shows that there are still statement items for each indicator that have a loading factor value of less than 0.70. On work discipline variable, statement item No. 12 and No. 13 has a loading factor value of 0.232 and 0.413 respectively. The value of the loading factor on the employee skills variable statement No. 12 (0.545) and statement No. 17 (0.504). On the variable work motivation statement No.13 (0.436). On the work productivity variable, statement item No. 04 and No. 15 has a loading factor value of 0.324 and 0.470 respectively. A loading factor value of less than 0.70 indicates that the statement item is declared invalid.

Discriminant Validity

The next validity test is discriminant validity testing. This test is based on the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value. The AVE value is good if it has a value greater than 0.50 (Ghozali, 2017). The following are values from the AVE table:

Table 2.
Value AVE (Average Variance Extraction)

No.	Variable	AVE Value
1.	Work Discipline (X ₁)	0.615
2.	Employee Skills (X ₂)	0.610
3.	Work Motivation (Z)	0.633
4.	Work Productivity (Y)	0.652

Source: Results of analysis using SmartPLS 3.0. (2023)

Table 2. above shows the AVE value of the research model. It can be seen from the table that the AVE value for all research variables and research dimensions has a value above 0.50 so that the AVE value for discriminant validity testing is sufficient for further testing. Thus, the Discriminant Validity test has been fulfilled as well as the Convergent Validity test so that it can be concluded that the research model is valid.

Reliability Test (composite reliability)

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The Cronbach's Alpha test is used to measure the internal consistency reliability of multiple item scales with the provision that the value must be > 0.70 . Reliability assessment can also be carried out by observing Composite Reliability which is a statistical technique to test the true value of a variable provided that the reliability value of Composite Reliability is always higher than Cronbach's Alpha value as follows. The SmartPLS output results for composite reliability values can be shown in the following table:

Table 3.
Value Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha

Variable	Composite Reliability	Terms	Cronbach's Alpha	Discription	Terms
Work Discipline (X_1)	0.954	> 0.70	0.949	> 0.60	Reliable
Employee Skills (X_2)	0.962	> 0.70	0.957	> 0.60	Reliable
Work Motivation (Z)	0.963	> 0.70	0.958	> 0.60	Reliable
Work Productivity (Y)	0.960	> 0.70	0.955	> 0.60	Reliable

Source: Results of analysis using SmartPLS 3.0. (2023)

Table 3. above is a table of composite reliability values of the research model. The table shows that each variable has a composite reliability value above 0.70 with the lowest value of 0.954 from the work discipline variable (X_1) and the highest value of 0.963 from the work motivation variable (Z). From these results it can be concluded that the research model meets the value of composite reliability. While the Cronbach's alpha value from the table research model shows that each variable has a Cronbach's alpha value above 0.60 with the lowest value of 0.949 from the work discipline variable (X_1) and the highest value of 0.958 from the work motivation variable (Z). From these results it can be concluded that the research model meets the value of Cronbach's alpha. From the model above, it can be concluded that the model meets the Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha criteria so that the research model meets the Reliability criteria and is a reliable and reliable measuring tool.

4. Conclusion

Based on the results of the research, it is concluded as follows; Work discipline has a positive and significant effect on work productivity during the Covid 19 pandemic, especially at a Freight Forwarding Service Company in DKI Jakarta, namely the KCU Jakarta Premier 13000 Post Office. Work skills did not have a significant effect on work productivity during the Covid 19 pandemic at a Freight Forwarding Service Company in DKI Jakarta, namely the KCU Jakarta Premier 13000 Post

Office. Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work productivity during the Covid 19 pandemic at a Freight Forwarding Service Company in DKI Jakarta, namely the KCU Jakarta Premier Post Office 13000. Work motivation did not mediate the influence of work discipline on work productivity during the Covid 19 pandemic at a Freight Forwarding Service Company in DKI Jakarta, namely the KCU Jakarta Premier 13000 Post Office. Work motivation mediates the effect of employee skills on work productivity during the Covid 19 pandemic at a Freight Forwarding Service Company in DKI Jakarta, namely the KCU Jakarta Premier 13000 Post Office.

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